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Research Article

Practical View Of Shushkamuladyam Tail Liniment Preparation

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is the most ancient healthcare system and it is practiced widely in India. Many herbal medicines or remedies individually or in combination have been recommended in various medical treatments for the cure of different diseases. Shushkamuladyam tail an Ayurvedic oil is used in the treatment of Shoth (Sprain) or inflammation. Acharya focus on preparation of drug and quality of drug. Herbal oil is the important Ayurvedic formulation which is used in various diseases to decrease pain and swelling of inflammation or Shotha. In this paper we have explained standard procedure of shushkamuladyam tail Liniment preparation. Preparation of oil as per Sharangdhara Samhita, and preparation of Liniment with the method of water in oil emulsification.

INTRODUCTION

The main aim of Ayurveda is to maintain health of healthy person and to make disease free to diseased person. Ayurveda is an ancient health science which is totally based on basic principles. The aim of Ayurveda is proved by many Acharya by applying various Ayurvedic fundamentals and some of them is Ayurvedic Treatment. Acharya Sharangdhara has described the method of Ayurvedic tail preparation. Liniment is prepared from the oil using the method of water in oil emulsification by using soap emulsifier.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Required material for the preparation of the Shushkamuladyam tail Liniment are listed below

1. Dried Shukshamulak
2. Dried Punarnava
3. Dried Devdaru
4. Dried Rasna
5. Dried Shunthih
6. Dried tila Taila
7. Non-Burner
8. Steel Container
9. Stirrer
10. Distilled Water
11. Air tight plastic Bottle for packing
12. Glycerine soap.

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Methods Preparation of Oil :

1. Collection of Drugs / Dravya to be used in the preparation of oil

- Dried Shushkamulak
- Devadaru
- Punarnava
- Shunthi
- Rasna

2. Preparation of Kalka

3. Preparation of Kwatha

4. Filtering of Kwatha by palm cloth

5. Adding oil to Kwath

6. Adding Kalka to Kwath oil.

7. Boiling up to the siddha Lakshan of oil preparation appears.

8. Filtration of oil.

Collection of Drug:

Til Tail

Wet Shushkmulak

Punarnava

Shunthi

Devdaru

Rasna Kalka

Dried Shushkmulak

Prepared Liniment :

Preparation of Liniment :

Soap	2.7 gm
Distilled Water	10 ml
Prepared Oil	10 ml

Continue stirring upto make emulsion. Adding drop by drop distilled water in Emulsion upto Liniment consistency (Milky white) then Liniment is packed in Air tight plastic bottle.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Sharangdhar samhita has explained the preparation of oil with the help of Kwath / Kalka which can be prepared from eight dried drugs or from wet drugs. Here due to unavailability of wet drugs we have used the dried drugs for preparation of Kwatha and kalka. Preparation of Liniment with the help of emulsion is of two types 1) Oil in water type (o/w) 2) Water in oil type (W/o). In O/w type oil is dispersed phase and water is continuous phase. There are mostly used in finally Bases used in this type is gum acaria, fragacanth, methyl cellulose, saponins, synthetic substances etc.3 In water in oil type Emulsions, water is in dispense phase and oil is in continuous Phase. Emulsifying base used in this method is wool fat, resins, beeswax, soaps, mostly used externally. In this Liniment preparation is done with the help of water in oil type method to be used as external local application in the condition pain and swelling due to trauma contains closed wounds not open. Wounds like sprain inflammation etc.5

RASPANCHA PANCHAK OF DRAVYA

Dravya	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipak	Prabhav
Punarnava	Tikta	Laghu	Shita	Katu	Shothhar
Devdaru	Tikta, Katu, Kashay	Snigdha, Laghu	Ushna	Katu	Shothhar
Rasana	Tikta	Guru	Ushna	Katu	Shothhar
Shunthi	Katu	Laghu, Snigdha	Madhur	Ushna	Shothhar
Shushkumulak	Katu	Tikshna, Laghu	Ushna	Katu	Shothhar

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